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Economic growth and greenhouse gases emissions

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Abstract

Economic growth is often stated as a critical parameter to disturb global sustainability. The environmental effects of economic growth are explained by the environmental Kuznets curve (EKC). Unfortunately, this inverted U-shaped relationship does not hold for greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions. Several theoretical and empirical studies have stressed the failure of GHG to follow an inverted-U path. The paper investigates if a positive relationship between GHG emissions and the level of economy in case of Greece exists. Data analysis supports the hypothesis that there is a positive correlation between GHG emissions and GDP in Greece since the GHG emissions increase as the GDP increase.

Keywords: GHG; economic growth; Kuznets curve; environmental economics.

1. INTRODUCTION

The environmental effects of economic growth have been receiving increasing attention by many economists in recent years. There are studies that investigate the relationship between environmental quality and economic growth. The common point of all studies is that the environmental quality deteriorates in early stage of economic growth and improves in later stage as an economy develops. This systematic relationship between income change and environmental quality has been called the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) [1].

Economists have proposed several reasons for the relationship between income and pollution emissions. Increasing economic growth, structural changes and increasing demand for environmental quality are some of the obvious reasons [2]. Therefore, the economic growth - pollution relationship is affected by the size of economy, the technology progress, the demand for energy, the demand for environmental quality, the education level and the policies for environmental protection. The aim of this paper is to review previous studies with regards to GHG emissions - GDP relationship and investigate if there is a positive relationship between GHG emissions and the level of economy in case of Greece.

The paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 presents the literature review with respect to income - environment relationship. Section 3 deals with results and discussions of the analysis while in Section 4 the conclusions of the analysis are drawn.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The EKC hypothesis predicts an inverted-U-shaped relationship between income and pollution. As the income of an economy grows, pollution emissions level grows first, reaches a peak and then starts declining after a threshold level of income has been crossed. Although the EKC hypothesis applies to some air pollutants, is not holding for all pollutants [3]. Theoretical and empirical

research examines the explanatory power of EKC hypothesis with respect to the greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions since GHG are responsible for global warming.

Environmental degradation is the result of increasing economical activity. The governments need to play a key role in reduction of these environmental consequences. Unfortunately, in most cases, for transboundary pollution problems, international governments cannot adopt local solutions. GHG are special pollutants that create global, not local, disutility. In the case that individual policies want to control the climate change, the net benefits of a GHG emissions stabilization program will not arrive until early in the 24th century, and the costs of this policy for current and near-term future generations are relatively large [4]. The EKC hypothesis only exists for local/regional pollutants, such as particulate matter, oxides of nitrogen, carbon monoxide and sulfur oxides [5,6]. Other studies suggest that further growth in income is likely to lead to a worsening in world pollution rather than to an improvement. These authors base their conclusion on the expectation that the rapid increase in emissions from currently developing countries will more than offset the potential decline in developed country emissions [2,7].

Several theoretical and empirical studies have stressed the failure of GHG to follow an inverted-U path. Global pollutants such as carbon oxides either increase monotonically with income [8,9] or else have turning points at high per capita income [10,11]. Income level is one necessary condition for improving the environmental quality and decreasing the CO₂ emission intensity, but it is not a sufficient condition. Empirical evidence supports the positive relationship between CO₂ emissions per capita and GDP per capita over time [12,13,14]. A relatively small number of wealthy countries could approach the turning point but this is rather impossible for the total of the countries [15,16]. It seems that, because of the rapidly economical growth of some populous developing countries [17,18] and the increasing rates of energy demanding in developed and developing countries [19], GHG emissions will continue to increase.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

European Union (EU) has already committed to contribute to the decrease the GHG emissions that come as a result of human activities. Within the bounds of commitments that derive from the Kyoto Protocol, EU has to decrease according to article 4 of the Protocol, its emissions by 8% for the period 2008-2012. The arrangement of the obligations of the parties has composed the agreement of the Summit of Ministers of Environment in June 1998. According to the European agreement of emission distribution (decision 2002/358/EU), Greece is committed to decrease the emission increase during 2008-2012 by 25% compared to base year emissions (1990 for CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O emissions). 100 Mt CO₂ eq (emissions equivalent to CO₂) are appointed as emission base, meaning the emissions that each country had in 1990.

The paper investigates if a positive relationship between GHG emissions and the level of economy in case of Greece exists. The results are interesting because of the commitments that derive from the Kyoto Protocol for Greece. The National Observatory of Athens provided the GHG emissions data for the period 1995 – 2003 [20]. In this paper, following previous studies, we present the GDP per capita as an indicator for the level of economy. Most analysts have investigated the EKC hypothesis using GDP as measure of country income because changes in GDP reflect the effects of changes in economic structure as well as changes in income [2]. The GDP data, for the period 1995 – 2004, were obtained from the 2005 Eurostat yearbook of European Commission [21].

Table 1. GDP per capita (in pps) and GHG emissions in Mt CO₂ eq for Greece

Indicators	Years									
	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004
GDP*	11000	11500	12200	12700	13300	14300	15100	16400	17300	18400
GHG emissions **	114.49	117.90	122.85	128.10	127.42	132.32	133.58	133.55	137.64	;

Source: * European Commission, 2005. Europe in figures, Eurostat, year book.

** National Observatory of Athens, (2005). National Inventory Report, Athens.

Figure 1. GDP (* 100) and GHG emissions for Greece.

Figure 2. GDP (* 1000) - GHG emissions relationship for Greece.

As shown in Table 1 and Figure 1, the GHG emissions tend to increase and follow the upgoing level of economic growth. Data analysis supports the hypothesis that there is a positive correlation between GHG emissions and GDP in Greece. The GHG emissions increase as GDP increase. These observations agree with the literature review. It seems that GHG emissions do not follow an inverted-U path until now. As shown in Figure 2, the rate of GHG emissions' increase with a decreasing rate. This could be the result from the commitments of Greece by the Kyoto Protocol.

In Table 1 we can observe that Greece has already overstepped the limit of 25%, thus it will have to pay either the penalty for the violation of the agreement, or the cost for the permission to continue to emit GHG over the allowed level. This observation agrees with the forecasts of Scenario for Expected Evolution (SEE) for the rights of gas distribution of Greece for the period 2005-2007 [22]. Out of the results of the forecast of gases in SEE, we conclude that within current decade a significant increase of 39.2% in GHG emissions is expected in Greece, which for the year 2010 exceeds considerably the target of confining the increase of gases during 2008-2012. All above taken into account, environmental policies are being planned and investments are being promoted, so that Greece can manage to succeed in the goals of the Kyoto Protocol.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The relationship between income level and different types of emissions depends on many factors. The EKC hypothesis is holding for certain types of environmental damage, such as pollutants with more short-term and local impacts, rather than those with more long-term, and global impacts (GHG). Since the ECK curve is not holding for all pollutants, we cannot argue that economic growth will solve the environmental problems. In future, governments should adopt legislative and economic policies about GHG emissions, climate change and energy, focused on sustainable development, such as the increase in use of renewable energy sources, cleaner production methods and new pollution control equipment. The collaboration between developed and developing countries on new technologies would be efficient [23], because of the rapidly economical growth of some populous developing countries and the transference of the most polluting industries from the rich countries toward the poorest ones that observed. Since education level contributes to the demand for environmental quality [24,25], sustainable development education may play a key role for people awareness and environmental protection in case of Greece.

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